

The Influence of Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing on the Decisions to Visit at Museum Sandi Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: This study was motivated by the importance of effective marketing strategies in increasing interest in visiting educational destinations, particularly museums. Museum Sandi in Yogyakarta, as the only cryptography museum in Indonesia, utilized event marketing and social media especially TikTok as promotional tools targeted at the younger generation. This study aimed to determine the extent of the influence of event marketing and social media marketing on the decision to visit Museum Sandi. This research applied a quantitative approach using survey methods through a closed-ended questionnaire. The sample consisted of 90 respondents who were visitors or potential visitors to Museum Sandi. The analysis revealed that both event marketing and social media marketing individually had a significant positive impact on the decision to visit. When tested together, these two variables also demonstrated a strong influence in encouraging visit decisions. Thus, it could be concluded that this research result, on well designed event marketing and social media marketing strategies enhanced the effectiveness of Museum Sandi's marketing communication.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the largest archipelagic countries in the world, with more than 13,000 islands and a coastline of about 108,000 km. Its natural and cultural richness makes it a favorite tourist destination for both local and international visitors. Tourists come to enjoy Indonesia's mountains, beaches, cultural villages, and historical sites. One of the most famous tourist cities is Yogyakarta, known for its strong cultural heritage and educational tourism. The city has many museums that not only display historical objects but also serve as places for learning, research, and recreation.

Based on data from the 2017 Yogyakarta Tourism Statistics, there are around 30 museums in the city, each with its own unique cultural and historical value. One of them is Museum Sandi, located in Kotabaru, Yogyakarta. The museum is in a Dutch colonial building that was once used as the Ministry of Foreign Affairs office in 1947. It was officially opened by the Head of the National Cyber and Crypto Agency and the Governor of Yogyakarta. The museum displays collections such as ciphers, encryption machines, and secret documents used during Indonesia's independence struggle from 1945 to 1949. These collections show the important role of secret communication in the nation's fight for freedom.

To attract more visitors, Museum Sandi uses event marketing and social media marketing strategies. Event marketing involves holding events that give visitors a fun and memorable experience. One of the museum's biggest events is Codephoria, which includes e-sport competitions, cybersecurity seminars, workshops, and exhibitions. These activities make the museum more interactive and appealing to the public. At the same time, Museum Sandi also uses TikTok (@museum.sandi) to promote its activities and collections. Through short and creative videos, the museum connects with the younger generation and builds interest in visiting. This approach helps increase brand awareness and attract more people to come. This research aims to find out how much Event Marketing (X1) and Social Media Marketing (X2) affect people's decision to visit Museum Sandi. The results are expected to help museums improve their promotional strategies and support the growth of cultural tourism in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

According to William J. Stanton (2019:8), marketing is a whole system of business activities designed to plan, price, promote, and distribute goods or services that can satisfy the needs of buyers, both existing and potential buyers. This definition emphasizes that marketing is not just an activity of selling products, but a series of integrated processes to create value for consumers and meet their needs in an effective and efficient manner. Marketing is a series of processes that involve planning, implementing, and managing various activities to create, offer, and deliver value from a product, service, or brand to consumers. The main goal of marketing is to meet market needs and wants, build long-term relationships with customers, and generate profits for the company or organization. Marketing activities cover various aspects, such as market research, product development, pricing, promotion, distribution, and after-sales service, which are carried out in an integrated manner to achieve customer satisfaction and support the achievement of business goals.

Event Marketing

According to Kotler and Keller (2016:8), event marketing is a marketing activity that focuses on organizing and managing events with the aim of creating a memorable experience for the audience, so that it can strengthen brand image and increase customer loyalty. This event serves as an effective means of communication to convey marketing messages directly to consumers. Event marketing is not just limited to physical events; in the digital era, virtual or hybrid events (a combination of physical and online) are also gaining popularity, especially in utilizing social media and technology to expand the reach of the event. Event marketing is a marketing strategy that involves organizing events to promote a product, service, or brand by creating a live experience that can build an emotional connection between visitors and the brand. Event marketing indicators, as follows: 1) Involvement, 2) Interaction, 3) Immersion, 4) Intensity. 5) Individuality, 6) Innovation, 7) Integrity.

Social Media Marketing

According to Pham and Gammoh (2015:10), social media marketing is a process carried out by companies in creating and promoting activities related to online marketing on social media platforms. The goal is to offer value to stakeholders, namely increasing awareness, recognition, recall, and action on brands, products, or services offered by the company. There are several indicators in Social Media Marketing according to Pham and Gammoh (2015), namely: 1) Context, 2) Communication, 3) Collaboration, 4) Connection.

Decision to Visit

According to Kotler and Keller (2016:11), the decision to visit is part of the consumer decision-making stage, which includes five main steps: need recognition, information search, choice evaluation, decision to visit, and post-visit behavior. In the context of tourism, this decision is not only driven by the desire to fulfill recreational or entertainment needs, but is also influenced by social, cultural, economic, and emotional factors. Visiting decisions refer to the process by which individuals or groups select and decide to visit a particular destination based on various factors that influence their preferences. This process is influenced by needs, motivations, perceptions, and evaluation of available information about the destination. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), there are several indicators regarding visiting decisions, namely: 1) Recognition of needs, 2) Information search, 3) Alternative evaluation, 4) Decision to visit, 5) Post-visit behavior.

Hypothesis Formulation

H1 : It is suspected that Event Marketing partially influence the decision to visit Museum Sandi in Yogyakarta.

Research conducted by Mehetabel (2023), which found that event marketing partially has a positive and significant effect on visiting decision.

H2 : It is suspected that Social Media Marketing partially influence the decision to visit Museum Sandi in Yogyakarta.

Research conducted by Darmawan et al (2024) who discovered that social media marketing has a positive influence on visiting decision.

H3 : It is suspected that Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing simultaneously influence the decision to visit Museum Sandi in Yogyakarta.

Research conducted by Mehetabel (2023) and Darmawan et al (2024) state that event marketing and social media marketing have a positive and significant effect on visiting decision in their research.

III. METHOD

The scope of this research discussion is the influence of event marketing and social media marketing on the decision to visit at Museum Sandi Yogyakarta. The type of research used in this study is quantitative research. Quantitative research according to Ahyar and Juliana Sukmana (2020:24), quantitative research focuses on the use of data in the form of numbers in the entire research process, from data collection, analysis, to data presentation. The quantitative method was chosen because this study aims to measure the influence of Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing on the decision to visit Museum Sandi at Yogyakarta statistically.

This approach allows the collection of numerical data that can be analyzed using statistical techniques to test the established hypotheses

The population of this study is limited to 145 visitors in the number of visitors to the Codephoria event on 14 and 15 December 2024 and in one particular age group or educational background, including all visitors who have experience with the Codephoria Event and 612 visitors in November 2024, namely when the viral content was uploaded on TikTok social media. The sample of this study is 90 respondents selected through purposive sampling which is the selection of samples based on specific characteristics (Sugiyono 2019). The consideration referred to is the criterion applied in this research, which are the respondent have attended the Codephoria 3 event held at the Museum Sandi, have ever seen or visited TikTok @museum.sandi, the decision maker to visit the Museum Sandi.

Data were collected using a questionnaire that was distributed online via Google Forms. The questionnaire sent focused on the relationship between Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing on visiting decisions. That measured using a five-point Likert scale. The research instrument was tested for validity and reliability, followed by descriptive analysis, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, coefficient of determination testing, and hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULTS

Validity Test

According to Kurniawan & Puspaningtyas (2016:97) said that the Validity Test is a test conducted to determine the validity/accuracy/accuracy of a question item in measuring the variable being studied. The validity test will see whether the question items in the questionnaire actually measure the variable. In this study, the total number of samples (n) is 90 respondents, and the degrees of freedom (df) are calculated using the formula $df = n - 2$, resulting in $df = 90 - 2 = 88$. With $df = 88$ and a significance level of 0.05 (5%), the critical r table value is 0.2072. The following are the results of the validity test using IBM SPSS Statistics 27:

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	r Hitung	r Tabel	Sig	Results
Event Marketing (X1)	X1.1.1	0.736	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.1.2	0.753	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.2.1	0.721	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.2.2	0.796	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.3.1	0.795	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.3.2	0.750	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.4.1	0.800	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.4.2	0.711	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.5.1	0.717	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.5.2	0.671	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.6.1	0.586	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.6.2	0.652	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.7.1	0.770	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X1.7.2	0.723	0.2072	0,001	Valid
Social Media Marketing (X2)	X2.1.1	0.848	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.1.2	0.751	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.2.1	0.817	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.2.2	0.809	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.3.1	0.885	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.3.2	0.830	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.4.1	0.764	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	X2.4.2	0.690	0.2072	0,001	Valid
Decision to Visit (Y)	Y.1.1	0.770	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.1.2	0.848	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.2.1	0.777	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.2.2	0.866	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.3.1	0.860	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.3.2	0.799	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.4.1	0.677	0.2072	0,001	Valid

	Y.4.2	0.687	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.5.1	0.752	0.2072	0,001	Valid
	Y.5.2	0.772	0.2072	0,001	Valid

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 1, it shows that all questionnaire items for the variables Event Marketing (X1), Social Media Marketing (X2), and Decisions to Visit (Y) are valid, as each item's r value is greater than r table (0,0.2072) and has a significance level < 0,05.

Reliability Test

According to Kurniawan & Puspaningtyas (2016:97) Reliability Test is a test that is done to determine the reliability (level of confidence) of a question item in measuring the variables being studied. The reliability test was calculated using the IBM SPSS Statistics 27 application program with the Cronbach Alpha method. The variable is said to be reliable if it provides a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60. Based on the processing results in this study, the results of the reliability test are as follows:

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Standar
Event Marketing (X1)	0,931	14	0,60
Social Media Marketing (X2)	0,917	8	0,60
Decisions to Visit (Y)	0,926	10	0,60

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table 2 of variable reliability test results, show that all variables Event Marketing (X1), Sosial Media Marketing (X2), and Decisions to Visit (Y) have good reliability levels, exceeding the threshold of 0,6.

Normality Test

According to Sutha (2021:244), normality testing is a test to measure whether the data obtained has a normal distribution so that it can be used in statistics. The regression model meets the normality assumption if the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows its direction or if the histogram shows a normal distribution pattern. The results of the normality test in this study can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1. Normality Test Result

Source: IBM SPSS Statistic 27, Processed Data (2025)

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that the normal P-Plot graph in the above image shows that the data points are located around the diagonal line or in alignment and form a diagonal line. The data is normally distributed. The normality assumption is fulfilled.

Heterocedasticity Test

According to Nugraha (2022:71), the heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether there is a variance inequality of the residuals is not the same for one observation and another does not have a certain pattern. This unequal pattern is indicated by unequal values between one residual variant. The symptom of unequal variance is called the heteroscedasticity symptom. The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity Test Results
 Source: IBM SPSS Statistic 27, Processed Data (2025)

As can be seen from the scatterplot in Figure 2, the data points are scattered above and below 0 on the y-axis without forming a specific pattern. Thus, it can be said that the data is free from heteroscedasticity, which means that the assumption is met.

Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2018:107), the multicollinearity test aims to examine whether the regression model shows a correlation among independent variables. A good regression model should not have correlation among the independent variables. Then the variables are not orthogonal. Orthogonal variables are independent variables that are uncorrelated. To determine whether there are symptoms of multicollinearity, it can be seen from the magnitude of the Tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values. The results of the multicollinearity test in this study are shown in the table below:

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity		Explanation
	Tolerance	VIF	
Event Marketing (X1)	0.509	1.966	No Multicollinearity
Social Media Marketing (X2)	0.509	1.966	No Multicollinearity

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on table 3, it can be seen that the event marketing variable (X1) and social media marketing variable (X2) have a tolerance > 0.1, which is 0.506. In addition, the VIF value of both variables is 1.966 < 10. Thus, the independent variables can be said to be free from multicollinearity symptoms.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis of independent variables (X variables) whose effects on the dependent variable (Y variable) are calculated, with more than one variable. In this study, there are two independent variables, namely two free variables (X), which are event marketing (X1) and social media marketing (X2). Here are the results of the multiple linear regression data analysis processed using IBM SPSS 27 Program Application:

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std.Error
(Constant)	1.077	2.315
Event Marketing (X1)	0.496	0.051
Social Media Marketing (X2)	0.341	0.080

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, a regression equation was obtained that shows the relationship between event marketing and social media marketing on the decision to visit the Sandi Museum. The analysis results indicate that both independent variables, namely event marketing and social media marketing, have a positive influence on the decision to visit.

This means that the better the implementation of event marketing, such as the interactive Codephoria event that involves many communities, the higher the tendency for visitors to decide to visit the Sandi Museum. Similarly, the more attractive and

relevant the content published through social media, particularly TikTok @museum.sandi, the greater its influence in shaping visitors' interest and decision to visit.

Therefore, it can be concluded that a marketing strategy combining events and social media can significantly contribute to increasing public visitation decisions to the Sandi Museum. The combination of both has proven effective in reaching a broader audience and building emotional connections with potential visitors.

Coefficient of Determination

According to Sugiyono (2017) the Determination Coefficient (R²) is used to determine how much the independent variable can explain the dependent variable. The value of the determination coefficient is in the range of zero (0) and one (1). Here are the determination calculation results for each variable as follows:

Table 5. Coefficients of Determination Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.890	0.792	0.787	2.345

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on table 5 above, the coefficient of determination (R²) results show that the adjusted R square coefficient obtained is 0.787 and the R² value is 0.792.

Partial Test (T test)

Partial tests are used to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Partial hypothesis testing is carried out using the T test (Roflin & Riana, 2022). The t table value is determined with a significant level of 0,05. The t table value is obtained by looking at df = (n-k-1) where n is the sample size and k is the number of independent variables at a 5% significant level. The table value for a sample size (n) = 90 and the number of independent variables (k) = df = 90 - 2 - 1 = 87 is obtained as the table value = 1.987.

Table 6. Partial Hypothesis Testing Results

Model	t count	t table	Sig.	Explanation
Event Marketing (X1)	9.636	1.987	< 0.001	Significantly influential
Sosial Media Marketing (X2)	4.245	1.987	< 0.001	Significantly influential

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on table 6, which contains the t-test results, shows events that are interesting, consistent, and emotionally engaging have been proven to increase visitor interest and decision-making. This shows that the direct experiences built during events can strengthen positive perceptions of museums and foster a desire to visit.

Simultaneous Test (F test)

Simultaneous hypothesis testing is a hypothesis test to determine the significance of the simultaneous effect of independent variables on dependent variables (Roflin et al., 2022). The Ftable is obtained by calculating the value of df = n - k where n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables for α = 0,05. This study has a df₂ value of 90 - 2 - 1 = 87. The F table value for df = 87 is 3.09.

Table 7. Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing Results

F count	F Table	Sig.	Significance Level	Explanation
165.324	3.09	0,000	0.05	Significantly influential .

Source: Processed Data (2025)

From Table 7, this means that the combination of promotional strategies through events and social media collectively explains the variation in visitor behaviour. A marketing strategy that is designed to be integrated and consistent between offline (events) and online (social media) can have a powerful effect in encouraging people's intentions and decisions to visit Museum Sandi.

V. DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Event Marketing on Decisions to Visit

The study shows that event marketing (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the decision to visit Museum Sandi, with a regression coefficient of 0.496 and a significance level of < 0.001. This means that improving event marketing strategies directly

increases visitors' willingness to visit. Engaging and innovative events that provide enjoyable experiences and emotional connections encourage visitors to return and recommend the museum to others. These findings support Kotler and Keller's (2016) view that event marketing effectively builds personal and emotional relationships between a brand and its audience, as well as Irna et al. (2020), who found that elements like entertainment, novelty, and engagement significantly influence satisfaction and visit intention. Therefore, strategically designed and audience-oriented event marketing is crucial for attracting more visitors, and Museum Sandi should continue to innovate in organizing creative events to sustain public interest.

2. The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Decisions to Visit

The regression results show that social media marketing (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the decision to visit Museum Sandi, with a regression coefficient of 0.341 and a significance value of < 0.001 . This indicates that the more effective the social media marketing strategy, the higher the likelihood of visitors deciding to come. In particular, TikTok plays a crucial role in delivering information, building engagement, and shaping public perception through educational, interactive, and entertaining content that sparks curiosity and interest to visit the museum directly. This supports Mangold and Faulds' theory that social media functions as a hybrid marketing tool capable of influencing consumer behaviour through informal communication. By implementing strategies such as visual storytelling, visitor testimonials, and event videos, museums can enhance awareness and visitation intentions. Therefore, Museum Sandi should continue to strengthen its social media marketing efforts as an effective communication platform, especially to attract the younger generation who rely heavily on social media for information.

3. The Influence of Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing on Visitation Decisions

The regression results show that event marketing (X1) and social media marketing (X2) together have a significant influence on the decision to visit Museum Sandi, with an R Square value of 0.792, meaning that both variables explain 79.2% of the variation in visiting decisions, while the remaining 20.8% is influenced by other factors. This high value indicates that combining experiential marketing through events with a strong digital presence on social media is highly effective. Event marketing provides emotional engagement and direct experiences, while social media marketing extends reach, maintains digital relationships, and keeps public interest alive after the event. The synergy between the two creates a continuous communication effect, as visitors share their event experiences online, enhancing organic promotion and strengthening the museum's modern image. In line with current digital trends, where consumer decisions are driven by visual content and peer recommendations, the integration of engaging event marketing and interactive social media strategies forms a comprehensive and effective approach to increasing visitor interest. Therefore, Museum Sandi should continue to apply and innovate within these two strategies to sustain public engagement and visitation growth.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted on 90 respondents who visited the Yogyakarta Sandi Museum, as well as data analysis using descriptive tests, multiple linear regression tests, T tests, and F tests, several important points can be concluded as follows:

1. Event Marketing has a Significant Effect on Decisions to Visit.

Partial test results (t test) show that the event marketing variable has a positive and significant influence on visiting decisions. With a regression coefficient value of 0.496 and a significance level of < 0.001 , it can be concluded that an increase in event marketing strategies will encourage an increase in visitors' decisions to come to the museum. Fun, interactive, and emotional experiences created through events are proven to be able to form positive perceptions of the museum and encourage the intention to visit again.

2. Social Media Marketing has a Significant Effect on Decisions to Visit.

The social media marketing variable also shows a positive and significant effect partially, with a regression coefficient of 0.341 and significance < 0.001 . This indicates that TikTok social media is an effective means of communication in shaping interest and interest in visits through educational, interesting, and easily shared content.

3. Event Marketing and Social Media Marketing Simultaneously Have a Significant Effect on Decisions to Visit.

The simultaneous test (F test) resulted in a calculated F value of 165.324 which is much greater than the F table (3.09) with a significance level of 0.000. This shows that together, event marketing and social media marketing make a very significant contribution in shaping visiting decisions. The R^2 value of 0.792 also shows that 79.2% of the variation in visiting decisions can be explained by these two variables.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations can be made:

1. The analysis results show that the Immersion and Intensity indicators have the highest mean values in the Event Marketing variable (average above 4.40). This indicates that the events held have been quite effective in creating a deep and memorable experience for visitors. However, the mean value for the Integrity indicator is slightly lower (around 4.21), which means there is still room for improvement in terms of trust and perception of professionalism. Museum Sandi can improve the clarity of event information, consistent event duration, and the communication of the tangible benefits of the events held. Training for event organisers in public speaking, time management, and communication can also strengthen participants' positive perceptions.

2. From the descriptive analysis results, the Context and Communication indicators in the Social Media Marketing variable obtained a mean value above 4.30, indicating that social media content is quite relevant and communicative. However, the Connection indicator had the lowest mean value (4.21), indicating that strengthening emotional connections and follower loyalty can still be improved. Museums can develop a more personalised approach, such as creating storytelling content from the visitors' perspective, holding interactive Q&A sessions, or featuring behind-the-scenes content that connects followers with the museum team. These strategies can build stronger relationships and audience loyalty.
3. Descriptive analysis shows that the Recognition of Needs indicator has a very high mean value (4.74), but Alternative Evaluation is in the range of 4.03. This indicates that although needs and interests are already high, potential visitors still consider other alternatives before finally deciding to come. Museums can strengthen their competitive advantage through a clear unique selling proposition, such as Instagram-worthy photo facilities, exclusive collections, or interactive programmes not available at other museums. It is also recommended to strengthen visitor testimonials on social media as positive considerations for potential visitors.

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